

Enhance your Confidence with Dental Bleaching: A Case Report

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Abstract

Managing tooth discolouration involves a range of different protocols for clinicians and patients in order to achieve an aesthetic result. There is an increasing public awareness in the appearance of their teeth and management of tooth discolouration may be inter-disciplinary and involve both vital and non vital teeth. Vital teeth can be easily treated with low concentration hydrogen peroxide products safely and effectively using an external approach and trays. The international organization for standardization (ISO) defines tooth bleaching as “removal of intrinsic or acquired discolorations of natural teeth through the use different concentrations of bleaching agents, sometimes used in combination with the application of auxiliary lights. Bleaching is an oxidative process that alters the light absorbing or light reflecting nature of the tooth increasing its perception of whiteness.

Key words: Vital teeth bleaching, Pola office plus, Discoloration, 37.5% hydrogen peroxide, In-office bleaching.

Introduction

Nowadays, individuals are not just content with healthy teeth, but also want to have a perfect smile. With the increase in aesthetic concerns, individuals often visit dental clinics for a whiter smile.¹ The majority of these individuals are not satisfied with the colour of their teeth. Teeth are considered as one of the most important feature of an attractive face. It is generally said that whiter teeth enhance the beauty of person's smile.² Vital bleaching procedures for the treatment of discoloration are a more conservative and cost-effective approach compared to resto-rative treatments.¹ Bleaching treatment can be carried out by the dentist in-office or at home by the patient under the guidance of the dentist.³ High concentrations of Hydrogen peroxide, Carbamide peroxide, Sodium perborate are used to provide fast, safe and very effective bleaching.⁴

Indications of Bleaching Agent

It has been reported that tooth discolorations with the best prognosis for whitening are the followings:

1. Yellowing of the teeth without any systemic or developmental cause (food, smoking, aging, staining)
2. Mild fluorosis staining
3. Mild tooth darkening due to trauma
4. Mild tetracycline staining.

Contraindications Of Bleaching Agent

1. Do not use on pregnant or lactating women.
2. Do not use on children under 14 years of age.
3. Do not use the Gingival Barrier on any persons having known resin allergies.

4. Do not use Bleaching agent on any persons having known peroxides allergies.
5. Bleaching agent will not lighten any restorative materials.
6. Do not use on patients with extremely sensitive teeth.

Case Report

An 18 years old, male patient came to the Department of Conservative Dentistry And Endodontics with chief complaint of discoloration of teeth. On examination, patient showed the presence of yellowish brown stains on all upper and lower anterior teeth. (Fig. 1)

Fig. 1 Pre-operative

Radiographic examination was done to check for the presence of periapical pathologies. Oral prophylaxis and polishing was done before commencing the treatment. Teeth color shade was verified using a color shade guide (Vita Classical). (Fig. 2)

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Fig. 2 Shade selection

Armamentarium

In this case, we used Pola-office plus which contained 37.5% Hydrogen peroxide (Bleaching Agent) and potassium nitrate (which acts as a desensitizer) and gingival barrier to protect gingiva. (Fig. 3)

Fig. 3 Gingival barrier and Pola office bleaching agent.

Bleaching Procedure

Soft tissue management: Gingival barrier was used to isolate & protect the soft tissues. (Fig. 4, Fig. 5)

Fig. 4 Application of gingival barrier

Fig. 5 Curing of gingival barrier

Application of bleaching agent

Bleaching agent was applied as a homogeneous mix over the teeth using applicator tip and activated for 8 minutes with the help of bleaching light according to manufacturer

instructions. (Fig. 6, Fig. 7). We used two bleaching cycles for good aesthetic result.

Fig. 6 Application of bleaching gel

Fig. 7 Activation of bleaching gel with the help of bleaching light

After finishing the bleaching procedure, remaining bleaching agent was removed using wet gauge piece and water spray with high suction tip, after that final polishing was done with ultra dent ultra proTxProphy polishing paste. Patient noticed marked improvement in tooth color with more enhanced smile. (Fig.8). Post-operative instructions had given to patient.

Fig. 8 Post-operative

Discussion

Nowadays there are multiple esthetic treatment options available in the field of dentistry, bleaching is one of them. Before starting the bleaching procedure, proper clinical evaluation and history taking is important to know the etiology responsible for tooth discoloration and the degree of discoloration.⁵ Bleaching is a de-colorization or whitening process that can occur either in the form of solution or gel and applied on the tooth surface.

According to AMERICAN DENTAL ASSOCIATION "Dental Bleaching is a treatment modality involving oxidative chemical reactions that alter the light absorbing and or reflecting nature of a material structure, thereby increasing its perception of whiteness".³

The effectiveness of vital dental whitening depends on many factors, such as the concentration/pH of the whitening agent, application duration, chemical additives, and reminerali-

zing agents used.⁶ Number of various brands of bleaching agents with various concentrations are available in the market. Pola office plus consist of 37.5% hydrogen peroxide and potassium nitrate, so patients experience low post operative sensitivity.⁷ Hence in this case, Pola office plus was used as a bleaching agent.

With in-office bleaching, both proper isolation and protection of mucosal tissues are essential. Dentists may also wish to consider prescribing NSAIDs prior to treatment since post-treatment sensitivity is unpredictable. There are many factors known to increase sensitivity such as high concentration of H₂O₂, high enamel permeability, prolonged use of bleaching agents, heat and light during the application of accelerator.⁸ Sensitivity issues have led some manufacturers to add desensitizing agent in order to minimize the side effects produced by peroxide radicals.⁹ A diagnosis of the etiology of the discoloration as well as discuss with the patients regarding their aesthetic expectations is mandatory.¹⁰

Conclusion

Based on the clinical results reported with professional vital tooth bleaching, it is a viable, esthetic treatment for the discoloured dentition, its conservative nature and little, if any, risk makes it an important part of an esthetic dentistry.

In-office bleaching has gained a lot of popularity in the general public. Many patients are now aware that in-office bleaching is a procedure that many dentists offer and is a great way to get a fast and immediate change in the colour of their teeth.

The average number of in-office bleaching for maximum whitening of teeth is three with a range of 1 to 6 times, so the patient should be prepared for additional in-office bleaching procedure.

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